

QUIZ

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Why do you need to give credit to the author of the information?

- To avoid plagiarism, because it is wrong to quote someone's work and not give them credit.¹**
- To appreciate the information you have cited.
- To be fair to the author.
- For copyrights motives.

2. What is an in-text citation?

- Refers to citing a piece of work including the page number.
- Refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself.²**
- Refers to the parenthetical citing of citation.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

² Ibid., 6.

Refers to citing following the style guide.

3. **How many spaces go after a period?**

One space should be typed after any punctuation.³

There is no space after a period.

Two spaces should be typed after any punctuation.

After a period, put three spaces to start the next line.

4. **What is a style guide?**

Refers to writing a document following American English.

Refers to writing an academic paper following the rules and guidelines of the university.

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.⁴

It is the way British students who write their academic papers.

5. **What kinds of questions do researchers seek to answer?**

The appropriate questions for researchers are practical.

Experienced researchers answer conceptual questions.

The most appropriate questions are practical and applied questions.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 18.

⁴ Ibid., 24.

- Experienced researchers know that different readers expect them to ask and answer conceptual questions, practical questions, and applied questions.⁵

6. **What is a research argument?**

- This means reasoning out your readers about your information.
- A research argument resembles an amicable conversation in which you and your imagined readers reason together to solve a problem whose solution they don't yet fully accept.⁶
- It means reasoning using evidence to reach a sound conclusion.
- This involves imagining your readers' questions and try to answer them.

7. **How do you quote while avoiding plagiarism?**

- An accurate quotation is crucial to the scholarly enterprise, so you must use only reliable, relevant sources, transcribe words exactly as they are in the original, or properly modify them, accurately report the sources in your bibliography or reference list.⁷
- Ensure to cite the exact names of the author.
- Write words in your style, then quote the author.
- Include the word 'modified' in your citation.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16–17.

⁶ Ibid., 36.

⁷ Ibid., 208.

8. **What is a run-in quotation**

- Means putting the attributing phrase in the middle of a quotation and setting it off with commas.
- Means enclosing the exact words in your text.
- This means enclosing the exact words quoted in double quotation marks when quoting a passage of fewer than five lines.⁸**
- Means weaving a quotation more tightly into the syntax of your sentence, such as with the word that, do not put a comma before it.

9. **What do you understand by a case study in research?**

- Refers to an intensive description and analysis of a phenomenon, social unit, or system bounded by time or place.⁹**
- Refers to the description of a setting and its participants.
- Analysis of the data for themes, patterns, and issues.
- Study of a social group in its natural setting.

10. **It is very important to cite sources of information. What does a list of works cited mean?**

- It is the provision of the publication information for each of the sources that were cited in the paper
- It is writing a reference page.
- It is the citing of the sources of your data.

⁸ Turabian, 208.

⁹ Dale Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 11.

- It is the 'bibliography' or the 'references' listed at the end of the book.¹⁰

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.